

Reprinting and Linking the Past: Creating a Nationwide Georeferenced Directory of Fixed- Line Telephone Subscribers, 1881-1984

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Summary

This paper describes the processes of digitally encoding and georeferencing a major new decennial Great Britain-wide micro-level dataset of fixed-line telephone subscribers for the period 1881–1984). Using scans of historical telephone directories, we develop and extend novel methods of digital data capture and use a range of geographies to assign locations to individual residential subscribers. We then map the coverage of each decennial dataset and estimate the adoption rates of telephony across Great Britain over the entire study period. We describe how these data enable (a) detailed geodemographic analysis of the adoption of fixed line telephony and (b) onomastic (family names-based) analysis of the mixing of long-established populations over the late 19th and 20th centuries. We conclude by assessing the importance of the work for linking historical and contemporary geodemographic analysis of Great Britain.

KEYWORDS: Historical GIS, Telephone Directories, Intergenerational Analysis, Innovation Diffusion, Geodemographics.

1 Introduction

Past intergenerational studies of British population movements and local demographic composition have utilised two individual level cornerstone resources: the Linked Consumer Registers (LCRs)¹ for 1997 to the present day and the Integrated Census Microdata (I-CeM, available for most of the 1881-1921 British censuses. Together they have underpinned a rich body of research on the distribution of

¹ From 2026, according to the GeoDS's blueprint, the LCRs (Linked Consumer Registers) will be rebranded as Smart Census Data (subject to confirmation).

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long-established British surnames (Cheshire and Longley, 2012; Cheshire, 2014; Kandt, Cheshire and Longley, 2016), intergenerational analysis of demographic change (Van Dijk *et al.*, 2019; Kandt, Van Dijk and Longley, 2020), and intergenerational social mobility (Longley, Van Dijk and Lan, 2021). Nevertheless, census data protection requirements² mean that the next post-1921 Census data will not be available until after 2051³. Onomastic (family name) analysis is thus not possible for the years between the 1921 Census and the earliest LCR (1997) because of a dearth of individual level digital name and address registers. It has thus hitherto been impossible to link historical geodemographic classifications (Lan and Longley, 2021) to those pertaining to the recent past (e.g. Wyszomierski *et al.*, 2024) – thereby missing, *inter alia*, the interwar boom, post-war reconstruction and the expansion of fixed-line telephony, during that intervening period.

To fill in this gap in data coverage, we acquired access to a unique collection of scans of telephone directories for the period 1880 – 1984 phone book images, held by BT (British Telecom) Archives and made available for research through the UKRI Smart Data Research UK Geographic Data Service's (GeoDS: <https://geods.ac.uk/>). The data comprise c.1.6 million images, of about 1.2 TB in size. The raw data include year-by-year directories for most of Great Britain throughout this period, wherein each printed page of residential subscribers lists the surname (with initials or personal names, sometimes abbreviated) and the address of each consenting subscriber. Error-free digital encoding of this resource presents a Herculean task, and so our effort was focused on extracting subscriber details for census years (1881, 1891, ... 1981, plus the cancelled census year of 1941 and the final available year, 1984). This approach not only allows for the comparison and association between telephone directories and the other two datasets (historical census and LCRs) in the following analysis, but also defines a more manageable timeframe for this project.

2 Data

2.1 Previous work: 1881 – 1951 Selective Collection

Tanu *et al.* (2024) took the first step in exploring and organising part of the raw data, and laid down a customised processing pipeline. The bespoke digitisation of the BT (British Telecom) historical directories includes image organisation, image conversion, image preparation, Optical Character Recognition (OCR)⁴, text cleaning and separation into different fields and, finally, geocoding. This process was then applied to clean the first batch of the data, comprising the 1881 to 1921 directories

² The census is only made publicly accessible 100 years after its enumeration.

³ Because of the accidental destruction of Census Enumerators' Books (CEBs) in 1931 and the interruption by war in 1941.

⁴ Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is a technology for digitising and computerising handwritten documents, printed texts and natural images (Mori, Suen and Yamamoto, 1992; Islam, Islam and Noor, 2016). The typical workflow of an OCR model includes: image pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, classification and post-processing (Mittal and Garg, 2020).

and parts of the 1921 to 1951 London, Glasgow and Manchester directories, as the following Table 1 details.

Table 1 Metadata of the first batch of BT directories (Data compiled by Tanu, 2024)

Year	Cleaned and formatted	Geocoded
1881	London	only London
1891	National*	only London
1901	National	only London, Glasgow and Manchester
1911	National	only London, Glasgow and Manchester
1921	National	only London, Glasgow and Manchester
1931	only London, Glasgow and Manchester	only London, Glasgow and Manchester
1941	only London, Glasgow and Manchester	only London, Glasgow and Manchester
1951	only London, Glasgow and Manchester	only London, Glasgow and Manchester

*In some of the years, the dataset covers Northern Ireland fixed-line subscribers, while as subsequent analysis requires it to be associated with the historical census and the LCR, which do not cover Northern Ireland, these records will thus not be included as part of geocoding and analysis

2.2 Extending the digitisation: 1921 -1984

As the aim of this research requires explorations beyond 1921, up to 1981 (at ten yearly intervals, consistent with previous work), plus the closest year to the start of the LCR—1984, which the previously processed dataset did not fully cover, we made necessary adjustments to the processing pipeline to accommodate unique features of the directories for more recent years. These changes included optimised OCR, more adaptive regex rules for street name extraction, a dedicated function to capture the Subscriber Trunk Dialling (STD) codes with an STD code look-up table (to match the three digits with the names of telephone exchanges), etc. We applied these amendments to extend the previous work and to generate a comprehensive BT historical subscribers' directory (see Table. 2) during the selective period for study (decennial years between 1921 and 1981, plus 1984). It needs to be noted that, as not every place's directory was updated in every selected year, we have used some

near years' directories to make up the missing parts where possible.

Table 2 Number of entries for each year of the telephone directories

Year	Valid rows*
1921	407,165
1931	644,058
1941	533,254
1951	845,946
1961	1,807,721
1971	4,377,564
1981	5,510,421
1984	4,697,703

*The valid rows (available for subsequent spatial analysis and research) were defined as those residential entries with encoded surnames with no fewer than two letters and which can be found in the 1881-1921 historical censuses, and which have street names that can be extracted using bespoke regex rules.

Figure 1 Cumulative Coverage Map of BT Historical Telephone Subscribers Directories

2.3 Geocoding – Address Matching

After the cleaning and formatting stage, the extracted street names were then matched against OS AddressBase Premium addresses using a bespoke historical geocoding model developed by Lan and Longley (2019). The core idea of this model is to run a two-stage fuzzy address matching to compare

the historical addresses with contemporary addresses using, firstly a token set ratio⁵ comparison in the front for rapid identification of closely aligned addresses, followed by a Levenshtein distance calculation for residual searches using greater tolerance.

Street-level geocoding was chosen over coordinate-level precision because the project's primary objective is to aggregate historical addresses to telephone exchange areas—the consistent unit of analysis—and link them with surnames and contemporary IMD scores to hindcast intergenerational socio-economic dynamics (Longley, Van Dijk and Lan, 2021). This approach also delivers sufficient spatial resolution for street-level geodemographic analysis (Lan and Longley, 2021). As a case study, we picked a sample from the Donaldson exchange from the 1971 Edinburgh telephone directory to evaluate the quality of our geocoding. (Fig. 02).

Figure 2 2022 Population Density Map of the Donaldson Telephone Exchange Area (source: Scottish Census)

⁵ Token set ratio is a string similarity checker that measures the overlap between the tokens (words) in the query string and candidate string, allowing it to handle partial overlap and effectively accounting for variations in word order (Kumar, Sangwan and Sharma, 2024).

Figure 3 Pipeline of Fuzzy Address Matching Test (adapted from Lan and Longley, 2019)

Figure 3 presents the pipeline of the address matching test. Cleaned street names were extracted, and their associated thoroughfare abbreviations were expanded to full terms. The two stages address matching process then enabled matching of 1,614 of the 2,121 cleaned addresses – a 76.1% match rate. Of these, 1,560 entries (96.9%) were validated manually. The results suggested that the proposed address matching method could be scaled to the entire decennial (plus 1984) dataset.

Figure 4 Line Density Map of Matched 1971 Telephone Subscriber's Addresses in the Donaldson Telephone Exchange Area, Edinburgh

2.4 Geocoding – Telephone Exchange Geography

Address matching was further enhanced using digital telephone exchange boundaries. The telephone exchange network, since the deployment of the first British exchanges in 1879, had grown from geographically constrained and fragmented local networks, driven by the development of telecommunication technologies (e.g. the innovation of RAX⁶ and UAX⁷, and the introduction to the STD⁸ system), to a national network of telephone exchanges. The telephone exchange geography evolved rapidly over time, and there are no digital records of exchange extents for most of the study period. We thus use only the present-day telephone exchange boundaries to enhance our address matching endeavours.

These boundaries are used to enable fuzzy address matching within every telephone exchange area, to identify the most probable contemporary ABP (AddressBase Premium, an Ordnance Survey product) addresses of the entries in the historical directories.

3 Discussion and Future Work

This research provides a major new digital resource that not only tracks the adoption of fixed line telephony, but also the onomastic characteristics of its adopters. Our own research agenda includes:

- (a) Comparing the onomastic composition of the telephone directories at the beginning (1881-1921) and end (1961-1984) of the study period using the I-Cem and LCR resources, respectively. This will provide indicators of innovation adoption anchored to geographic context.
- (b) Describing the developing coverage of the resource, viz. (i) the parts of Great Britain in which residential lines were available and (ii) the parts of the country for which there are gaps attributable to missing directories or absence of relevant updates. This will allow us to develop a research design to investigate the contemporaneous diffusion of family groups and communication technology.
- (c) Quantifying the heterogeneity of telephone exchange areas, taking account of the distance

⁶ Rural Automatic Exchange (RAX) is a Strowger switch based automatic telephone exchange), which replaced the manual exchanges (UAX Project, 2008).

⁷ Unit Automatic Exchange (UAD) is an expandable automatic exchange, which allows the exchange to accommodate more telephone lines by adding more units of Strowger switches (UAX Project, 2008; Freshwater, 2019), and which also enabled the rural exchanges to be parented on a larger exchange in a nearby major town, creating a ‘parent-satellite’ hierarchical geography (Freshwater, 2019; ‘History of Telephone Numbers in the United Kingdom’, 2025).

⁸ Subscriber Trunk Dialling (STD) project classified the national telephone network into 639 “pricing groups”, and with Group Switching Centre (GSC) acting as the parent switch for all the smaller local exchanges (those single UAXs), to automate the entire national telephone network (Blackwell, 2016; ‘Subscriber Trunk Dialling’, 2025).

travelled by bearers of family names identified as non-local. This will result in measures of the integration of people/family groups and places into Great Britain's space economy.

- (d) Where possible, attributing georeferenced family residences to the classes of historical (Lan and Longley, 2021) and contemporaneous (Wyszomierski *et al.*, 2024) geodemographic classifications. This will enable (i) person-based classifications of the human and social capital of members of different family groups and (ii) place-based analysis of the neighbourhoods that make up Britain's urban and regional system.

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Paul Longley is Professor of Geographic Information Science at University College London, where he also leads the Geographic Data Service – part of the UK Economic and Social Research Council’s Smart Data Research UK programme. His research interests are focused on socioeconomic and demographic applications of Geographic Information Science, including geo-temporal demographics, urban modelling and inter-generational social mobility. His work often entails creation and use of large and complex datasets. He is a co-author of *Geographic Information Science and Systems* and has held various journal editorial roles, including of *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* between 1997-2007.